

Building a Culture of Reuse:

An Analysis of Reusable Software and Policies for Institutional Libraries

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Agenda

1. Context at Virginia Tech University Libraries (VTUL)
2. Discussion of problem statements
3. Methodology - Web Survey
4. Results
5. Interventions and design considerations
6. Conclusion

Openness at VT

Increased value for open knowledge at a University-level

- Recently publish Policy 13000, Policy on Intellectual Property
- Open Knowledge Committee in Library
- Blogs, resources, events, and publishing all promoting openness
- Open Access Subvention Fund

Policy on Intellectual Property

No. 13000

1.0 Purpose

OPEN **ACCESS**

The logo consists of a large orange padlock icon that is open, with a circular shape inside the bottom loop.

Open@VT

What about the “backend” work?

Example work that is overlooked

- Documentation
- Policy
- Software
- Wikis
- LibGuides
- How-To's
- Tools

Reasons work may not be shared

- Lack of standards
- Unwilling or unable to share
- University/organization policies
- I don't want to
- I don't know how to

Context at VTUL

Pursuing a CoreTrustSeal
co-application with the Academic
Preservation Trust + new platform

lots of...

- Documentation and policy development
- Homegrown software development
- Software README development and reuse instructions
- Intentional information released to the public
- Community review and feedback on policies
- Policy-driven software development

Research Questions

Research Question 1

Are VTUL digital library resources understandable and reusable to VTUL stakeholders?

Research Question 2

Are VTUL digital library resources understandable and reusable to organizations external to VTUL, and how can we improve our resources for reusability?

We spend a lot of energy trying to create things from scratch when, frequently, another library may have already done something very similar.”

-- Meredith Farkas

Necessity of Policy & Software Reusability

Policy

- Dictates consistent workflows and strategies
- Aids in self-audits or certifications
- Ongoing resource for referencing the “why” of decisions
- Trust

Software

- Improves software quality through broader testing in a community
- Promotes progress
- Promotes new concepts and methods faster
- Trust

Methodology

Internal Survey

- Distributed to our IT Advisory Group
- Informal, anonymous, vibe-check
- Questions:
 - As an IT Advisory Group member, are you familiar with the process for reviewing and approving policies for the digital library?
 - What was most understandable about this process?
 - What was the least understandable about this process?
 - Do you feel that you would reuse these policies in the future for your own work?
 - If yes, how so?
 - Do you feel that a colleague in other University Libraries would be able to understand and reuse the digital library policies for similar purposes?
 - Do you have any other comments you would like to include?

Web Survey (Virginia Tech IRB #22-430)

- 8 questions
- Designed to explore the impact of our open policies and open software outside of VTUL and collect feedback on how to make our resources more reusable based on community needs
- No questions required a response
- Distributed to listservs in the communities of digital libraries, digitization, software development, IT management, and digital curation, digital preservation, and on social media
- Survey results were anonymized and each questions' responses were condensed into broader topics for analysis

Survey Questions

1. What is your field?
2. Please indicate all of the areas your position interacts with in your organization [check from list]

Please navigate to

<https://apps.es.vt.edu/confluence/display/LIBDPLD/Digital+Library+Policy+and+Documentation>

3. How likely are you to reuse or adapt other digital library policy for your own work? [scale 1 - 5]
4. Regarding policy, what is the most important factor to you when you consider reusing resources? [check from list]

Please navigate to <https://github.com/vt-digital-libraries-platform>

5. How likely are you to reuse or adapt other digital library code for your own work? [scale 1 - 5]
6. Regarding digital library code bases, what is the most important factor to you when you consider reusing resources? [check from list]
7. If you wanted to make your digital library resources more reusable and discoverable, how might you go about doing so? [free text]
8. Do you have any other comments you would like to share regarding digital library resources? [free text]

Limitations

Informal Survey (Internal only)

- Distributed only to a single group within the Library
- Designed to take the pulse, not to gather significant information

Web Survey (External communities)

- Combining policy and software in the same survey may have deterred participation due to lack of experience in either field
- Scope is limited to only VTUL digital resources

Results

Informal Survey Results

- 50% response rate
- Limited awareness of the policy development and approval process
 - Some attribution to turnover in the group
- 75% think they may use/reuse policies
- 25% think other university's may use/reuse policies

Web Survey Results: Range of Respondents

49 complete responses

1. Field: top four fields were Digital Libraries/Archives (25%), Libraries (14%), Digital Preservation (11%), and Information Science (11%).
2. Department interaction: Digital Libraries, Information Technology, Digital Preservation (16%); Metadata (14%); Special Collections (12%); Digital Imaging (10%); Write-in (3%)
 - a. Write-ins: physical preservation and conversation, scholarly communications, leadership and administration, and access/discovery services.

Web Survey Results: Policy Feedback

3. Policy use/reuse:

- 1 (very unlikely): 10.64%
- 2 (not likely): 8.51%
- 3 (neutral): 21.28%
- 4 (likely): 27.66%
- 5 (highly likely): 31.91%

4. Important factors for policy reuse

- Ease of reuse or adaptation: 27.37%
- Relevance to your work: 25.26%
- Usability/understandability: 24.21%
- Accessibility: 11.58%
- Discoverability: 9.47%
- Other: 2.11%
 - Licensing, thoroughness

Web Survey Results: Software Feedback

5. Software use/reuse:

- 1 (very unlikely): 8.7%
- 2 (not likely): 26.09%
- 3 (neutral): 26.09%
- 4 (likely): 28.26%
- 5 (highly likely): 10.87%

6. Important factors for software reuse

- Ease of reuse or adaptation: 27.84%
- Usability/understandability: 26.8%
- Relevance to your work: 24.74%
- Accessibility: 8.25%
- Discoverability: 6.19%
- Other: 6.19%
 - Quality
 - Community involved in coding
 - Ability to cut and paste modules or snippets
 - Current staffing of library IT institution
 - Sustainability

Web Survey Results: Resource Reusability Strategies

7. Top Strategies:

- Storage on GitHub
- Clear documentation
- Clear licensing for reuse
- Promotion at appropriate conferences and listservs

Additional topics:

- Utilizing sitemaps for increased discoverability
- Improving the metadata quality of resources
- Providing resources specifically on how to implement software

Web Survey Results: Additional Comments

“Most likely to re-use simple modules with minimal (or no) external dependencies that solve singular issues”

“DOCUMENTATION.”

“There is very little in my work that I have not borrowed from somewhere or learned from someone else.”

“Usually we are closed in our Digital library software. It should be a complement component”

“It'd be helpful if people didn't go into something with the mindset that they are very special snowflakes who need to reinvent the g.d. wheel.”

Overall Web Survey Results

Informal survey indicates that we can do a much better job communicating policies within VTUL

Survey results indicate that people want to be able to see what resources other's have to ideally to reuse and adapt them

Interventions & Design Considerations at VTUL

Things We Will Continue

- Promoting resources at conferences
- Hosting policies and software in publicly accessible locations
- Documentation!
- Asking for feedback from colleagues
- Regular updates and reviews

Things We Will Improve

- Add clear licensing to all resources
- Improve documentation, particularly on decisions made and rationalization
- Promote via relevant listservs and social media
- Policies
 - Cite other policies we used for reference
 - Supplementary documentation that notes parts that are specific to VT
- Software
 - Increase guidance on how to use the software, common errors
 - Commenting

Long-term Goals

- Create templates that are more generalizable to other organizations
- Ingest resources to our digital library to assign identifier, handles, and embed metadata
- Improve metadata quality
- Utilize sitemaps for greater discoverability
- More integration with other metadata harvesters like DPLA

Cool Things We Can't Do Alone

Consortia that develops, shares, and maintains digital library resources in a single aggregated location

Policy edit-a-thons

(If this exists, let me know!)

Resources to Share - Feedback is Welcome!

Virginia Tech Digital Library Policy and Documentation

<https://apps.es.vt.edu/confluence/display/LIBDPLD/Digital+Library+Policy+and+Documentation>

Virginia Tech Digital Libraries Platform GitHub

<https://github.com/vt-digital-libraries-platform>

Virginia Tech Digital Libraries Platform About

<https://about.digital.lib.vt.edu/project/>

Feedback and Comments

- Software: Digital Libraries (digital-libraries@vt.edu)
- Policy: Digital Libraries (digital-libraries@vt.edu)
 - Alex Kinnaman (alexk93@vt.edu)

Thank you!

Questions?

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